

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

SOLVING PROBLEMS OF QUANTUM MECHANICS BY METHODS OF INTEGER THEORY

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Abstract

In the present review of the author's works, the calculation of the radiation spectrum of a hydrogen-like atom is described in detail using the principle of commensurability of conserved quantities, which is introduced by the author. The result obtained allows us to give a clear physical interpretation of Bohr's quantum hypothesis. It follows from the data obtained that the "resolved" states of quantum systems are the result of the need to fulfill the requirement of having a common measure of conserved quantities for all participants in physical interaction before and after interaction.

Keywords: principle of commensurability of conserved quantities, radiation spectrum of a hydrogen-like atom, Bohr quantization hypothesis, integer theory, resolved states of quantum systems, principle of causality

1. Introduction

Modern quantum mechanics and quantum physics successfully describe the world in which we live. Now there is no problem like the "ultraviolet catastrophe", which at the beginning of the last century led to the emergence of a new mechanics - quantum. But the fact that such a successful science contains an element of "fatal inevitability" of the correctness of this theory, about which the outstanding physicists R. Feynman and S. Weinberg write in [1], cannot help but cause constant dissatisfaction. How to understand *the reasons* for the behavior of quantum systems, overcoming its "magic"?

In [2], one of the creators of quantum mechanics, M. Born, writes that "... *the main feature of the new mechanics, obviously, is that some physical quantities can only take on discrete values, such quantities are called quantum.*" The concept of quantization was introduced into physics, as is known, by N. Bohr and M. Born further writes: "...*although the Bohr theory leaves the deep reasons underlying the momentum quantization rule completely mysterious, nevertheless, this rule turns out to be justified by the results obtained in the process of further development of the theory*". In our opinion, this is the key phrase of an outstanding scientist for understanding how the "mysterious causes of quantization" are substantiated by modern science - namely, they are substantiated with the help of numerous results obtained by theory and later confirmed by experiment. This is precisely the criterion for the truth of the hypothesis proposed by Bohr. But if we carry out the calculation of a certain interaction with the help of "mysterious quantization", and then we get confirmation of the prediction of this calculation in an experiment, do we really understand *the physical reasons why* Nature is arranged according to quantum laws? By carrying out appropriate calculations, we are able to predict the behavior of objects, those we know *how* Nature works, but *why* it is arranged in a "quantum" way - we do not have an answer to this question. The very *reason* for the quantization of Nature remains still mysterious.

In order to unravel the true reason for the need to quantize the physical quantities of Nature, one more non-trivial step must be taken. It must be assumed that physical objects, when interacting with each other, exchange conserved quantities (energies, momenta, angular momentum, etc.) not in an arbitrary way, but in such a way that the conserved quantity (let the energy) of interacting objects have a common measure for energy values up to and after the interaction. What is the common measure for two (or more) quantities? This means that both quantities can be measured with the same "meter" and express their values in integers of units of measure. It has been known since ancient Greece that the diagonal and the length of a square do not have a common measure, and this is because the diagonal of a square has a length of $\sqrt{2}$, i.e. expressed as an irrational number. For this reason, the diagonal of a square and its side cannot be measured by the same "meter" - *they do not have a common measure*. It is also well known from any complete course in higher mathematics that two (or more) quantities a and b always have a common measure if their ratio a/b is expressed by a rational number. And the presence of a common measure for quantities makes it possible to express their values using integers (it can be said differently - *each* of the commensurate quantities can be used as a "meter", that is *each* quantity can measure any counterpart from the set of commensurate quantities). But if physical quantities can be represented in the form of integers, then to solve the problem of the interaction of physical objects, one can then apply the methods of the theory of integers.

Such a hypothesis, i.e. the hypothesis of the need to fulfill the conditions of commensurability of conserved quantities in the interaction of physical objects (which we call *the principle of commensurability of conserved quantities*) allows us to solve problems of quantum mechanics using the theory of integers. One of the central problems of physics is the problem of radiation from a hydrogen-like atom. The solution to this problem using the commensurability hypothesis is described in great detail in [3], but in this article we will

reproduce its presentation for the integrity of the perception of the proposed text.

2. Solution of the problem of radiation of a hydrogen-like atom

For a substantiation of a possibility and necessity to use discrete methods of description of the physical reality, we will calculate spectral series of hydrogen atom, using the principle of commensurability. Let it be the simplest mechanical atomic model, namely, as a proton with the localised electron rotating around. In process of radiation of atom three physical objects are involved: the proton, the electron, and a the quantum.

Let the initial atom state will be an excited one, being as much as close to the ionized state. Conservation laws of energy-momentum we will with necessity write in the relativistic form. We will transfer in the coordinate system related to the excited atom. Its energy will be noted in the form:

$$E_{at}^2 = (m_0 + m_{eff})^2 c^4 \quad (1)$$

Here $m_0 c^2$ is energy of atom in the basic, non-excited state, $m_{eff} c^2$ is a virtual value of excitation energy of atom, as much as close to ionisation energy E_{ion} , c is velocity of light.

After irradiation of the quantum having energy E_q , the excited atom obtains an momentum \mathbf{p}_{at} , which is equal on quantity and opposite in the direction to a quantum momentum \mathbf{p}_q :

$$p_{at}^2 = p_q^2 = E_q^2 / c^2 \quad (2)$$

After irradiation of quantum by atom, we will denote energy of atom as:

$$E'_{at}{}^2 = (m_0 + m'_{eff})^2 c^4 + p_{at}^2 c^2, \quad (3)$$

here $m'_{eff} c^2$ is a virtual value of excitation energy of atom in lower energy state (i.e., after quantum irradiation), $p_{at}^2 c^2$ - energy of atom motion after quantum irradiation.

Let us determine energy of the radiated quantum (it is a difference of energies of an excited atom before radiation of quantum and after its radiation) as:

$$p_q c = E_{at} - E'_{at} = (m_0 + m_{eff}) c^2 - \sqrt{(m_0 + m'_{eff})^2 c^4 + p_{at}^2 c^2} \quad (4)$$

Let us rewrite this expression:

$$\sqrt{(m_0 + m'_{eff})^2 c^4 + p_{at}^2 c^2} = (m_0 + m_{eff}) c^2 - p_q c$$

Let us raise it in the second degree, remove the brackets, reduce and group like terms:

$$(m_{eff}^2 - m'_{eff}{}^2) c^4 + 2m_0(m_{eff} - m'_{eff}) c^4 = 2E_q(m_0 + m_{eff}) c^2 \quad (5)$$

From here

$$E_q = \frac{\left\{ m_{eff}^2 \left[1 - \left(\frac{m'_{eff}}{m_{eff}} \right)^2 \right] c^2 \right\}}{2(m_0 + m_{eff})} + \frac{\left[m_0 m_{eff} \left(1 - \frac{m'_{eff}}{m_{eff}} \right) c^2 \right]}{m_0 + m_{eff}} \quad (6)$$

Considering that $m_{eff} \ll m_0$, it is possible to write with high accuracy:

$$E_q = \left(\frac{m_{eff}}{2m_0} \right) \cdot m_{eff} c^2 \left[1 - \left(\frac{m'_{eff}}{m_{eff}} \right)^2 \right] + m_{eff} c^2 \left[1 - \frac{m'_{eff}}{m_{eff}} \right] \quad (7)$$

If to neglect a term of the order of $m_{eff}/2m_0$ in last equality, for energy of the radiated quantum we will finally obtain:

$$E_q \approx m_{eff} c^2 \left[1 - \frac{m'_{eff} c^2}{m_{eff} c^2} \right] = E_{ion} (1 - m'_{eff} c^2 / m_{eff} c^2) \quad (8)$$

From the last relation it is seen that if all values of energy of irradiated quanta E_q have a common measure with the same initial energy of the excited atom E_{ion} (they must have it by definition), then ratio $m'_{eff} c^2 / m_{eff} c^2$ should be rational and among a plurality of rational ratios, certainly, will be also numbers 1/4, 1/9, 1/16 etc., that will correspond to energy of quanta of Lyman series:

$$E_{q1} = E_{ion} (1 - 1/4), E_{q2} = E_{ion} (1 - 1/9), \text{ etc.}$$

If to take (let it is now formal) other admissible rational numbers, for example, 31/36, then, having substituted it in expression (9), we will obtain:

$$E'_{q1} = E_{ion} \left(1 - \frac{31}{36} \right) = E_{ion} \cdot \frac{5}{36} = E_{ion} \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{9} \right) \quad (9)$$

Further, the rational number 13/16 is also admissible, substituting it in (9), we will obtain:

$$E'_{q2} = E_{ion} \left(1 - \frac{13}{16} \right) = E_{ion} \cdot \frac{3}{16} = E_{ion} \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{16} \right) \quad (10)$$

Accordingly, the number 79/100 will give the energy of the quantum:

$$E'_{q3} = E_{ion} \left(1 - \frac{79}{100} \right) = E_{ion} \cdot \frac{21}{100} = E_{ion} \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{25} \right), \text{ etc.} \quad (11)$$

It is seen that energy of quanta E'_{q1} , E'_{q2} , E'_{q3} give the Balmer series. It is clear that remaining spectral series can be simply obtained using such formal method.

However, it is also seen that among plurality of admissible rational values of ratios $m'_{eff} c^2 / m_{eff} c^2$ for description of corresponding series, only specific values are suitable, i.e., there are some selection rules of the "necessary" values of the rational ratios, which correspond to experiment. It has appeared that for an explanation of the fact of the selection of the "necessary" values one should use requirements of commensurability in the act of irradiation of the excited atom not only for energies and momenta, but also for the third conserved quantity – an angular momentum of the atomic system.

Let us still use the simplest mechanical atomic model, where the localised electron rotates round the

proton on a certain orbit and possesses a certain angular momentum:

$$J = r_{el} \times p_{el} \quad (12)$$

Here, r_{el} is a radius of electron rotation on the orbit, p_{el} is the momentum of an atomic electron.

Values of the angular momentum of the electron in atom *before and after irradiation* of quantum by the atom should remain commensurable *by definition*. But, if the momentum of the atomic electron p_{el} is expressed by an integer of a unit of measure, hence, for integrality of J , the radius r_{el} should also be expressed by an integer, (or rational, that is the same) but, certainly, of its own units of measure. In other words, *values of radii of rotation of the electron in atom must be commensurable with some least value $r_{el,min}$* . Using below the mechanical atomic model, we will determine these integral-valued, i.e. allowed, values of radii of rotation of the electron. On each of orbits a centrifugal and centripetal forces should be counterpoised:

$$F_{eff} = m_{el}V_{el}^2/r_{el} \quad (13)$$

where V_{el} is velocity of the electron on the orbit, m_{el} is electron mass:

$$F_{ctf} = -e_1 \cdot e_2/r_{el}^2 \quad (14)$$

where e_1 and e_2 are elementary charges of the electron and proton respectively, i.e.:

$$\frac{m_{el}V_{el}^2}{r_{el}} = -\frac{e_1 \cdot e_2}{r_{el}^2} \quad (15)$$

This relation can be also written as:

$$m_{el}V_{el}^2 \cdot \frac{r_{el}}{r_{el}^2} = -\frac{e_1 \cdot e_2}{r_{el}^2} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{or } m_{el}V_{el}^2 \cdot r_{el} = -e_1 \cdot e_2 \quad (17)$$

From the last relation it is seen that for any integer r_{el} the product $m_{el}V_{el}^2 \cdot r_{el}$ *should remain constant*, as product $e_1 e_2$ in right member of the equality is constant. But, besides, for any r_{el} the requirement of commensurability for values J and J' , where J' is the value of the moment after irradiation, should be satisfied. To satisfy *simultaneously* requirements of constancy of $m_{el}V_{el}^2 \cdot r_{el}$ and the requirement of commensurability of the moments, r_{el} must vary on *the whole quadrate* of unities, i.e. it should be equal to 1, 4, 9, 16, ... etc. units of measure. Really, if r_{el} has varied not on the whole quadrate of units of measure, and, for example, it increased in two times then for invariance of $m_{el}V_{el}^2 \cdot r_{el}$ in (17) velocity of electron V_{el} should decrease accordingly in $\sqrt{2}$ times. Then quantity of the momentum after irradiation should become:

$$J' = m_{el} \cdot \left(\frac{V_{el}}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \cdot 2r_{el} \quad (18)$$

But as before irradiation it was:

$$J = m_{el}V_{el}r_{el} \quad (19)$$

Then ratio J/J' becomes *in this case* be irrational, and it is *intolerable* in the proposed model, as in this case the momentums have no common measure.

If the atom potential energy is described by U/r function, an allowed values of r_{el} , varying on the whole quadrate of units of measure $r_{el,min}$ (they ensure commensurability of values of the moments of momentums) determine allowed values of the potential energy, namely, U_{max} , $U_{max}/4$, $U_{max}/9$, ... etc., where $U_{max} = E_{ion}$.

Radiation of the exited atomic system can be carried out only at the expense of decrease of its intrinsic energy. So, transition of the atomic system from one higher value of the potential energy in a lower one is accompanied by quantum irradiation, for example:

$$E_{q1} = \left(U_{max} - \frac{U_{max}}{4}\right) = E_{ion} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4}\right); E_{q2} = \left(U_{max} - \frac{U_{max}}{9}\right) = E_{ion} \left(1 - \frac{1}{9}\right); \dots \text{ etc.} - \text{ we have spectral Lyman series.}$$

Balmer series will be obtained from transitions between $U_{max}/4$ and remaining, lower energy states:

$$E_{q1} = \left(\frac{U_{max}}{4} - \frac{U_{max}}{9}\right) = E_{ion} \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{9}\right); E_{q2} = \left(\frac{U_{max}}{4} - \frac{U_{max}}{16}\right) = E_{ion} \left(\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{16}\right), \text{ etc.}$$

Remaining series are obtained in the same manner.

Thus, regularities of transitions of hydrogen-like atomic systems from one excited state into another with quantum irradiation (or absorption), observed experimentally, can be explained by the necessity of performance of requirements of commensurability of energies, momentums, and the moments of momentums of these systems.

The result obtained is interpreted from the point of view of physics as follows. When interacting physical objects, quantities that are *absolutely* preserved cannot be transferred from one object to another with an accuracy of one or another sign (for example, if the value of a quantity is irrational, then with an accuracy of up to the tenth or hundredth decimal place, etc.), they must be conveyed by *the exact value* of the units of this quantity, because the conserved quantity does not disappear anywhere and does not appear from nothing. And such an accurate transfer of the quantity of a conserved quantity from one object to another can be performed only when the value of any conserved quantity will have a common measure *before and after the interaction* for all participants in the interaction - only such interactions *are resolved*.

In the above problem, it was not taken into account that the electron has its own mechanical and magnetic moments of momentums. Since both the mechanical and magnetic moments of an electron are conserved quantities, then, of course, in a scrupulous solution of such a problem, their values must also be taken into account. But this is a deeper solution to the problem of atomic radiation. It should be noted that *the principle of commensurability of conserved quantities* is universal, it allows solving many other problems. For example, in [3] a numerical solution of another classical problem of physics, the scattering problem, was also given, and *quantization over the scattering angles was obtained*, which is especially noticeable for large deviations of

the test particle, but it is important that such a solution was obtained under the assumption of the interaction of a *localized particle* with a force center (and not in the wave approximation of the particle-wave with *one wavelength*, which is determined by de Broglie's law).

When solving problems in physics using the theory of integers, it is extremely important to determine in each problem *what is the measure* of a conserved quantity, i.e. how to determine the magnitude of the measure, with what "meter" to measure this or that conserved quantity when describing the interaction, in order to obtain *an integer number* of units of measure. Some aspects of this complex problem are described in [4]. The solution of another applied problem on the physical foundations of polymorphic transformations in crystals using the concepts of the commensurability of conserved quantities is given in [5]. Philosophical aspects that arise when using the methods of the theory of integers in physics are discussed in [6].

3. Conclusion

The application of *the principle of commensurability of conserved quantities* in physics provides a physical justification for the Bohr quantization hypothesis, which underlies quantum mechanics. It can be argued in a sense that the principle of causality is returning to quantum physics, because there is a completely clear physical reason for explaining the "resolved" and "unresolved" states of quantum systems. So far, such states have been explained simply by the mathematical results of solving problems that were confirmed by experiment, without a physical explanation of *why* these solutions are true. But, in our opinion, the greatest dissatisfaction of both physicists and philosophers should be caused by the fact that in order to explain the experimentally confirmed diffraction pattern of the scattering of localized particles on a crystal lattice, one has to use the model of a *localized particle-wave with one value of the wave vector*, while the localized entity *must be presented* as a packet of waves. But the packet will inevitably spread out, about which M. Born writes very clearly and fairly in [2]: "...*there is a great temptation to try to interpret a material particle as a wave packet formed by the superposition of a certain group of waves. However, this tempting interpretation runs into insurmountable difficulties, because such a wave packet, generally speaking, is unstable and will spread out very soon*". It turns out that, on the one hand, a localized entity must be represented as a packet of waves,

but on the other hand, in order to explain the results of the experiment on the diffraction of *localized particles*, we are forced to represent this localized entity as a *single wave*, which has an infinite size in the direction perpendicular to the propagation vector. This is indeed an "insurmountable difficulty" both in physics and in philosophy, but it can be overcome using *the principle of commensurability of conserved quantities*.

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